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***IN VITRO* INHIBITORY EFFECTS OF *MUCUNA PRURIENS* AND *VETIVERIA ZIZANOIDES* ON SELECTED HUMAN BACTERIAL PATHOGENS**

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ABSTRACT

Indian herbal medicines have served as major source of medicine for prevention and treatment of many diseases including microbial infections. Emergence of multidrug resistance has limited the therapeutic options for antibiotics in the world. Hence, monitoring resistance is of paramount importance. The use of traditional herbal medicines in crude or refined form may help the treatment of microbial infections with two advantages, i.e. the cure is achieved and the chances of microbes becoming resistant are minimized. The herbal medicines have the advantage of producing minimum side effects when compared to the usual antibiotics. Therefore this study was undertaken to focus on the in vitro antimicrobial effects of two plants known for their medicinal value. Plant materials of *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanoides* were tested for their antibacterial activities on selected strains of bacteria namely, *Bacillus cereus* (ATCC13061) *Shigella flexneri* (ATCC 12022) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 6643). These activities were compared with standard antibiotic namely Broad spectrum antibiotics, Penicillin and Ampicillin. Antimicrobial activity was measured using the standard method of diffusion disc plates on agar and the MIC was calculated using dilution method. Our results clearly indicate that the plants *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanoides* have the antimicrobial properties.

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INTRODUCTION

During the last decades infectious diseases have threatened the lives of millions of people around the world. Even though pharmaceutical industries have produced a number of new antimicrobial drugs in the past, resistance to these drugs by microorganisms has increased. In general, bacteria have the genetic ability to transform and acquire resistance to drugs used as therapeutic agents. The initial introduction of new medicinal agents into the health care system some times requires information beyond that is recorded in libraries, relying instead on reports available through traditions and healers within a society [1]. Thus traditional medicinal practices, conserved over years by civilizations, can serve as an effective basis for the discovery and development of modern therapeutic drugs. The development of novel, efficient and inexpensive drugs is of great importance. In a constant attempt to improve the quality of life, men have used plants as a source of food, shelter, clothing, cosmetics and for seeking relief from hardships of life. Some plants are known as medicinals, because they contain active substances that can cause certain reactions leading to the cure of certain diseases caused by pathogenic organisms [2].

Knowledge of medicinal plants is the only means of therapeutic resource for some communities and ethnic groups and their use in various parts of the world contributes significantly to primary health care [3]. For centuries, medicinal plants have been used all over the world for the treatment and prevention of various ailments, particularly in developing countries, where infectious diseases are endemic and modern health services and facilities are inadequate. Many potent drugs have been purified from medicinal plants which range from antibacterial, anti malarial, anti cancer and anti diabetic [4,5]. The present study focuses on the antibacterial properties of two medicinal plants, namely, *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanoides* against the selected pathogenic microorganisms such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Mucuna pruriens is one of the popular medicinal plants of India and is a constituent of more than 200 indigenous drug formulations. It is widespread over most parts of the subcontinent and is found in bushes and hedges. This is a dry deciduous plant. All parts of the plant possess valuable medicinal properties and there is a heavy demand of this plant in Indian drug market. *M. pruriens* seeds are herbaceous forage and food legumes that have, for a long time found widespread usage as rotation crops for the management of various pests and pathogens as well in soil improvement and weed control [6]. Seeds of *Mucuna pruriens* are known to produce the unusual non protein amino acid 3(3,4-Dihydrophenyl)-L-alanine (L-Dopa), a potent neuro transmission precursor, i.e. at least in part, believed to be responsible for the toxicity of *Mucuna pruriens* seed. L-Dopa, a potentially neurotoxic agent is used in the treatment of Parkinson's disease, is found in relatively large amounts in *Mucuna pruriens* seeds [7,8,9]. It is also known that different parts of the plant are used for the management of several free radical mediated diseases, such as rheumatoid arthritis, diabetes, atherosclerosis, male infertility and nervous disorders in Ayurvedic system of medicine. Kumar and Muthu, 2010, Suresh *et al.*, 2010 have reported the anti oxidant properties of *M. pruriens* [10,11]. It is also said to be good aphrodisiac and a good nerve tonic. It is used to treat spermatorrhea and diseases of urinogenital system [12]. Anti inflammatory, diabetic and anti bacterial activity of *Mucuna pruriens* was reported [13].

Vetiveria zizanoides is a densely tufted grass. It can withstand extreme drought conditions. It has a wide pH range tolerance and grows in any soil type regardless of soil fertility and can withstand temperature as low as 9°C to as high as 95°C. It can withstand repeated mowing. Vetiver oil is supposed to have a nerve relaxant causing reduced mental stress. Chemical components of *Vetiveria* roots have very high fungicidal, bactericidal and insecticidal properties [14]. The oil is reported to be carminative in flatulence, colic and obstinate vomiting. It is regarded as a stimulant, diaphoretic, refrigerant, astringent and antimicrobial [15]. When applied externally it removes excess heat from the body and gives cooling effect [16]. Probably the high tensile strength of *Vetiveria* roots and the inherent microbial property on account of its essential oil makes the roots of the plant an ideal natural material for making compressed hardboards, panels etc [17]. The decoction of the roots is believed to dissolve kidney stones and the paste made from pounded fresh roots is considered as an abortifacient. Medicinally this plant oil is reported to be used as a carminative in flatulence and colic, as antipyretic and as anthelmintic [18]. *V. zizanoides*, It is locally applied to relieve pain [19]. Young leaves are used as fodder and good bedding for horses and cattle [20]. The leaves are also used for thatching purposes [21] At present the vast majority of studies on *Vetiveria zizanoides* are focused on the functions of soil waste correction, land reclamation, and hill side protection. The present study focuses on the antibacterial properties of two medicinal plants, namely, *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanoides* against the selected pathogenic microorganisms such as *Bacillus cereus*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials

Plant materials of *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanoides* were collected from their authorized Ayurvedic store in Chennai, India. Both the plants were identified and authenticated by reputed botanist.

Extraction from plants

The plant materials were dried in shade and powdered in a mechanical grinder. The powder of the plant materials were initially de-fatted with petroleum Benzene (60°C-80°C), followed by soaking it in 1000 ml of ethanol for 72 hrs. The extract was filtered using Whatman filter paper (No.1) and then was concentrated and dried at 45°C for ethanol elimination, and the extracts were kept in sterile bottles, under refrigerated conditions until further use. The dry weight of the plant extracts was obtained by the solvent evaporation and used to determine concentration in mg/ml. The extract thus obtained was directly used in the assay of antimicrobial activity.

Antibiotics

Broad spectrum antibiotics, Penicillin and Ampicillin were used as control drugs.

Bacterial Strains

The strains of microorganisms (*Bacillus cereus* (ATCC13061) *Shigella flexneri* (ATCC 12022) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 6643) were used. Pure plant cultures were ordered.

Determination of Antimicrobial Activity

Antimicrobial activity was measured using the standard method of diffusion disc plates on agar and the MIC was calculated using dilution method (Kirby- Bauer method).

Dilution Methods

Dilution susceptibility testing methods were used to determine the minimal concentration of antimicrobial to inhibit or kill the microorganisms. This was achieved by dilution of antimicrobial in either agar or broth media. Antimicrobials are generally tested in \log_2 serial dilutions (two fold).

Broth Dilution Method

The Broth Dilution Method is a simple procedure for testing a small number of isolates, even single isolate.

Preparation of microorganisms for experiment

The pure cultures of organisms were sub cultured in nutrient broth. They were inoculated, separately, into nutrient broth and kept at 37°C for 24 hours. Then, they were kept at 4°C until use.

Growth Method

At least three to five well-isolated colonies, of the same morphological type, were selected from an agar plate culture of a particular microorganism. The top of each colony was touched with a loop, and the growth was transferred into a tube, containing 4 to 5 ml of nutrient broth medium. The broth culture was incubated at 35°C for 8 hours. After the incubation period broth culture became turbid.

Disc Diffusion Method:

Mueller-Hinton Agar Medium

Mueller-Hinton Agar is considered to be the best for routine susceptibility testing of non-fastidious bacteria for the following reasons. It shows acceptable batch-to-batch reproducibility for susceptibility testing. Medium is transparent, so that the inhibition zone can be visualized clearly. It gives satisfactory growth of most non fastidious pathogens. A large body of data and experience has been collected concerning susceptibility tests performed with this medium.

Preparation of Mueller-Hinton Agar

Mueller-Hinton Agar was prepared from a commercially available dehydrated base according to the manufacturer's instructions. Immediately after autoclaving, it was allowed to cool in a 45^o to 50°C water bath. The freshly prepared and cooled medium was poured into glass or plastic, flat-bottomed Petri dishes on a level, horizontal surface to give a uniform depth of approximately 4 mm. This corresponds to 60 to 70 ml of medium for plates with diameters of 150 mm and 25 to 30 ml for plates with a diameter of 100 mm. The agar medium was allowed to cool to room temperature and unless the plate is used the same day, stored in a refrigerator. Plates were used within seven days after preparation unless adequate precautions, such as wrapping in plastic, have been taken to minimize drying of the agar. A representative sample of each batch of plates was examined for sterility by incubating at 30^o to 35°C for 24 hrs or longer.

Preparation of antibiotic stock solutions

Powders of the two antibiotics (Penicillin and Ampicillin) were brought from authorized medical shop. They were accurately weighted and dissolved in sterile distilled water in appropriate dilutions to yield the required concentrations. The stocks were kept in aliquots of 5 ml volumes and frozen at -20°C.

Preparation of plant extracts solutions for the experiment

The dried plant extracts were weighed and dissolved in sterile distilled water to prepare appropriate dilution to get required concentrations (1.0mg/ ml, 1.5mg/ ml, 2.0 mg/ ml, and 2.5 mg/ ml). They are kept under refrigeration.

Preparation of dried filter paper discs

Whatman filter paper (No.1) was used to prepare discs approximately 6 mm in diameter, which are placed in a Petri dish and sterilized in a hot air oven. After the sterilization, the discs were poured into the different concentration of broad spectrum antibiotics and into the prepared plant extract solutions and again kept under refrigeration for 24 hrs.

Figure 1: shows the Zone of inhibition of control drug Penicillin , Ampicillin M.pruriens and V.zizanoides on Bacillus cereus.

Figure 2: shows the Zone of inhibition of control drug Penicillin , Ampicillin M.pruriens and V.zizanoides on Pseudomonas aeruginosa.

Figure 3: shows the Zone of inhibition of control drug Penicillin , Ampicillin M.pruriens and V.zizanoides on Shigella flexneri.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reading of Minimum Inhibition Concentration

Minimum inhibition concentration was expressed as the lowest dilution which inhibited growth judged by lack of turbidity in the tube, because very faint turbidity might be given by the inoculum itself. The inoculate tube was kept in the refrigerator overnight and was used as the standard for the determination of complete inhibition. The plant extracts were found to be effective against the three selected bacterial species.

Reading Zone of Inhibition and Interpreting Results.

After 16 to 18 hrs of incubation each plate was examined. Once the resulting zones of inhibition came uniformly circular and in a confluent lawn of growth, the diameters of the zone of complete inhibition (as judged by the unaided eye) are measured, including the diameter of the disc. Zones are measured to the nearest mm using a ruler, which was held on the back of the inverted Petri plate. Clear inhibition zones indicated the presence of antimicrobial activity [22].

The use of medicinal plants in the world and especially in India, contribute significantly to primary health care. The antimicrobial medicinal plants are well documented. The results of different studies provide evidence that some medicinal plants might indeed be potential sources of new antibacterial agent even against some antibiotic resistant strains [23].

In the present study reveals that the two extracts from *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanioides* possess antimicrobial activities against *Bacillus cereus*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Figure 1, 2 and 3). The two extracts compared favourably with the standard antibiotics Penicillin and Ampicillin. *Mucuna pruriens* extract showed more activity than *Vetiveria zizanioides* extract. Both plants exhibited broad spectrum antibiotic activities. The results indicated that the extract of *Mucuna pruriens* has stronger activity than that of standard antibiotics and the extract of *Vetiveria zizanioides* has less activity than those of standards. Since ancient times, herbs and/or their essential oils have been known for their varying degrees of antimicrobial activities [24]. More recently, medicinal plant extracts were developed and proposed for use in food as natural antimicrobials. Antimicrobials are powerful but controversial tools. Food animals are often exposed to antimicrobial compounds to treat or prevent infectious diseases and/or to promote growth. The early history of supplementing animal feeds with antimicrobials parallels the isolation, identification and characterization of Vitamin B¹² in 1948. Further research in this area showed that several feed ingredients, including dried mycelia of certain fungi, were more potent as growth promoters in the diet of chicks than was vitamin B¹² alone. The reducing capacity of *Mucuna pruriens* was observed by the transformation of Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺ ions [25]. Thus this plant can serve as a potential indicator of its antioxidant capacity. Phenols are very important plant constituents and have scavenging ability due to their hydroxyl groups [26]. The phenolic compounds may contribute directly to the antioxidant action. It was suggested that polyphenolic compounds have inhibitory effects on mutagenesis and carcinogenesis in humans, when ingested up to 1 g daily from a diet rich in fruits and vegetables. Except for *Shigella flexneri*, *Bacillus anthracis* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Enterococci* may be resistant to Ampicillin and Penicillin because of production of low affinity Penicillin binding protein (PBPs) or less commonly because of the production of β Lactamase. The disc diffusion test can accurately detect isolates with altered Penicillin binding proteins but it will not reliably detect β -lactamase producing strains. The rare β lactamase producing strains are detected best by using a direct, nitrocefin based β -lactamase test [27]. Certain Penicillin, Ampicillin resistance *Enterococci* may possess high level of resistance. The disc diffusion test can not differentiate those with normal resistance from this high level resistance.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the results obtained in the present study, we conclude that the extract of *Mucuna pruriens* and *Vetiveria zizanioides* has significant antimicrobial activity. Further studies are on to isolate the active principles responsible for their antimicrobial activities.

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